

Historical and Comparative Analysis of Master's Level LIS Program in some of the Oldest Universities in India

Poonam Rani and Nirmal Kumar Swain

Department of Library and Information Science, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana

Several Universities in India are offering Library and Information Science (LIS) education at both UG and PG levels. In the present study, it was intended to examine the structure, curriculum and academic orientation of Master's level LIS programs in some of the oldest universities in the country. Further, it was also intended to examine how the traditionally offered LIS program has transformed in modern LIS education, incorporating the essentials of information and communication technology. For this purpose, data about the programs offered, duration, course content, pedagogy and accreditation status/grade, etc., were gathered from the official websites of the University of Calcutta, University of Madras, University of Bombay, and Banaras Hindu University. Besides, the official websites, the academic handbooks and NAAC reports of the institutions were also consulted. The findings suggest that though the LIS principles remain consistent, there is increasing emphasis on digital librarianship, knowledge management, and research methodology. It is concluded that the LIS education has to keep pace with emerging trends.

Keywords: Library and Information Science (LIS), universities in India, master level programs

The LIS education in India is said to have started in 1911 in a Baroda school financed by Maharaja Sayajirao Gaekwad III with the help of W.A. Borden, an American Librarian from the USA. However, the first systematic program at the University level was initiated by S.R. Ranganathan at the University of Madras and the Madras Library Association around the 1920s (Kumar, 2008). An American Librarian named Asa Don Dickenson initiated an apprentice training program at Panjab University, Lahore (Ameen, 2015). Andhra University introduced a post-graduate diploma in Library Science in 1935 (Singh, 2003). Later on, these programs were further expanded from 1930 to 1940, wherein many universities (Banaras Hindu University, University of Bombay, University of Calcutta and Delhi University) started these programs. It is reported (Kanchandani, 2019) that prior to independence, there were five universities providing programs in library science in India. These universities are Andhra University (in 1935), University of Madras (in 1937), BHU (in 1941), University of Bombay (in 1943) and University of Calcutta (in 1945). Among these two universities were such that where the diploma programs were started due to Dr. Ranganathan's efforts. Later on, Dr. Ranganathan moved to Delhi University, where he started a diploma in 1947 and after that a Master's in Library

Science in 1951. D.B. Krishna Rao was the first to get a Ph.D. in Library and Information Science in India in the year 1957. In the year 1972, the University of Delhi started M.Phil in Library and Information Science (Kumar & Sharma, 2010).

Shukla and Jaiswal (2025) in an interesting paper- The Landscape of LIS education in India, published in Annals of Library and Information Studies in June 2025, have highlighted the current scenario/status of LIS education in India. They have reported that out of the 56 Central Universities, 21 (37.5%) and out of the 488 state universities, 129 (26.43%) are running LIS programs in the country. With regard to the type of programs, they reported that Certificate, Diploma, B.Lib.I.Sc, M.Lib I.Sc. Integrated and PhD. programs are being offered. There are about 1074 total universities in the country and out of these, 430 are private universities, which are not included in the Shukla and Jaiswal study. Even if we ignore the private universities and take only the Central and State universities reported in Shukla and Jaiswal's study, the total comes out to be 544 and out of these, only 150(27.57%) are there where any of the LIS programs is running. It indicates that the discipline still needs to grow and flourish and as Kanchandani (2019) has said that though the LIS profession has undergone paradigm shifts owing to the technological changes yet it still needs to be revamped to go along the changes.

Jain, Kaur, and Babbar in an article about LIS education in India have reported that currently both the traditional as well as digital libraries both co exist in India, yet the LIS education in the country still needs to become receptive to the emerging situation, develop the required knowledge and skills. They have also emphasized the need for revamping the curricula and many of the institutions have done it, and many others are in process. In this transition phase, many traditional papers, like the history of books and libraries, have disappeared, and papers like computerized information networks and information retrieval have found a place.

In light of the above, the present study was planned to have a historical and comparative analysis of Master's level LIS programs in some of the oldest universities in India. The study was conducted with the following objectives

Author Note

Poonam Rani, Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak Haryana

Prof. Nirmal Kumar Swain, Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak Haryana

E-mail: drnkswain@gmail.com

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Poonam Rani, Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Science, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak Haryana

E-mail: poonamrohillal3@gmail.com

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the structure and curriculum of Master's programs in LIS in India's oldest universities.
- To evaluate how these programs align with current trends in digital librarianship and information technology.
- To examine accreditation standards (UGC, NAAC, AICTE) and their influence on LIS education.
- To suggest improvements for enhancing the global competitiveness of LIS programs in India.

Method

To achieve the objectives of the study, a mixed-method approach with a descriptive and comparative qualitative design was used. Four oldest universities of the Country were selected, these include the University of Madras, Mumbai, Calcutta, and Banaras Hindu University. The criteria were that these were the universities that started LIS education in the initial years. For the collection of information (data), the UGC website and NAAC reports were checked, besides the official websites of the selected universities and their academic handbooks for the courses, curriculum, faculty compositions, credit system, and selection criteria. Data were tabulated, and a comparative analysis was done, identifying the patterns, similarities, and differences among the selected institutions

in terms of the courses, content, etc.

Data Collection

Information was gathered from official university websites, academic catalogues, and regulatory reports (UGC & NAAC).

Universities Selected

University of Calcutta (est. 1857), University of Madras (1857), University of Bombay/Mumbai (1857), and Banaras Hindu University (1916).

Analysis Framework

Comparison based on curriculum structure, specialization courses, admission criteria, credit requirements, practical components, and use of ICT.

Data Analysis

Content analysis and comparative tabulation were used to identify common patterns and institutional differences.

Results and Discussion

The obtained data retrieved from the sources mentioned above from the four universities, the establishment of the university, the start of the LIS department, and the type of programme being run, are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive Data about the Universities

Establishment year of Department	Name of the University	Establishment Year of University	Programme offered
1931	University of Madras, Tamil Nadu	1857	M.Lib.I.Sc., PhD
1943	University of Mumbai, Mumbai	1857	M.Lib.I.Sc., PhD
1945	University of Calcutta, Kolkata	1857	B.Lib.I.Sc., M.Lib.I.Sc., M.Phil., PhD
1941	Banaras Hindu University, Uttar Pradesh	1916	MLIS, PhD M.A. in Manuscripto-logy

The results (Table 1) revealed that the University of Madras was the first to establish the Department of Library and Information Science in the year 1931. Then, the University of Mumbai (then Bombay) and Calcutta established the LIS departments respectively in the years 1943 and 1945. All these three universities were established in the same year, i.e. 1857. BHU was established in 1916 and started LIS in 1941. The Madras and Mumbai universities are running M.Lib.I.Sc. and PhD. Programs in LIS, whereas BHU is also running M.A. Manuscriptology besides M.Lib. I.Sc. and PhD. programs. Calcutta University has had B.Lib. I.Sc., M.Lib.I.Sc. M.Phil. (now discontinued) and Ph.D. Program.

Out of the four selected Universities (Table 2), only BHU is the central University, and it was graded 'A' by NAAC, but now the

university website is silent about the recent grading. Out of the three State universities, all are the earliest established universities in the country. The University of Madras and Mumbai both have 'A++', whereas the University of Calcutta was once awarded an 'A' grade, but the website is currently silent about it.

Table 2

NAAC Accreditation Status

Name of the University	Type of University	NAAC Accreditation
University of Madras	State	Grade "A++"
University of Mumbai	State	Grade "A++"
University of Calcutta	State	Grade "A"
Banaras Hindu University	Central	Grade "A"

Table 3

Faculty and Intake in Master's Level

Name of the University	Name of the Department	Teaching staff	M.Lib.I.Sc.
University of Madras (1857)	Department of Library & Information Science	3	20
University of Mumbai (1857)	Department of Library & Information Science	11	30
University of Calcutta (1857)	Department of Library & Information Science	10	20
Banaras Hindu University (1916)	Department of Library & Information Science	8	46

With regard to the availability of faculty in the four universities and admission intake, it was found (Table 3) it is found that Madras University is in a precarious situation as far as faculty is concerned, as it has only 3 faculty members. BHU has 8, and Mumbai and Calcutta universities have 11 and 10 faculty members respectively. It is important to note that only regular faculty are considered here. The intake in master's programs is also given in Table 3, from where it can be seen that in BHU it is 46, followed by Mumbai, with an intake of 30 students. The Madras and Calcutta University has an equal number of student intake, i.e., 20.

Results (Table 4) reveal that there is a wide variation in the credits at the master's level. University of Calcutta has the maximum 114 credits, followed by University of Mumbai, Madras, and BHU with

96, 87 and 80 credits respectively. It indicates the need for a uniform credit structure in the program as per the curriculum framework of UGC.

Table 4

Total Credits Including Core and Elective Courses at the Master's Level

Name of the University	Level/ Integrated/ or one year	Total Credits
University of Madras (1857)	M.Lib.I.Sc.	87
University of Mumbai (1857)	M.Lib.I.Sc.	96
University of Calcutta (1857)	M.Lib.I.Sc.	114
Banaras Hindu University (1916)	M.Lib.I.Sc.	80

Table 5

Courses Taught

Curriculum Elements	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Name of the University	Information in society	Foundation of the LIS profession	Information and Communication technologies	Research and Innovation	Information lifecycle management	Management for Information Professionals	Information Needs and User Services	Literacy and Learning
UNOM	√	×	√	√	√	√	√	×
MU	×	√	√	√	×	√	√	×
CU	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	×
BHU	√	×	√	√	√	√	×	×

Results (Table 5) reveal that information communication and technology, research and innovation, and management for information professionals are the courses that are there in all four universities. Literacy and learning are not taught in any of the

universities. Information in society and information life cycle management are the courses that are taught in all except Mumbai University. Information needs and user services are taught in all universities except BHU.

Table 6

Faculty & Selection Criteria for Master's Program in LIS

Name of University	Level	Eligibility admission	Department name	Faculty
University of Madras	M.Lib.I.Sc.	A Bachelor's degree in any subject from the University of Madras or any other University.	Library and Information Science	School of Information and Communication Studies
University of Mumbai	M.Lib.I.Sc.	A pass in B.Lib.I.Sc. from any recognized university with a minimum aggregate.	Library and Information Science	Inter-Disciplinary Studies
University of Calcutta	M.Lib.I.Sc.	Bachelor's in Library Science from a recognized university.	Library and Information Science	Education, Journalism & Library Science
Banaras Hindu University	M.Lib.I.Sc.	Bachelor's degree under at least 10 + 2 + 3 patterns with a total of 50% marks in aggregate.	Library and Information Science	Faculty of Arts

The findings (Table 6) indicate that the eligibility for the Master's program in Library Science is a Bachelor's degree with a certain percentage of marks in the University of Madras and BHU, whereas it is a Bachelor's degree in Library Science in Mumbai and Calcutta University. In all the universities, the LIS program is in different faculties. In Madras University, it is in the School of Information and Communications Studies, whereas it is in the faculty of Interdisciplinary Studies in Mumbai University. In Calcutta University M.Lib.I.Sc. The program is in the Faculty of Education,

Journalism and Library Science, whereas it is in the Faculty of Arts at BHU. It clearly indicates variations in eligibility norms and the Faculty in which LIS programs are being run.

Findings of the Study

The four oldest established universities in India started LIS education from 1931 to 1945. Only Calcutta University is running a Bachelor's program along with Master's and PhD; all others have only Master's level programs with PhD. BHU is also running M.A.

Manuscriptology. Both the University of Madras and Mumbai are NAAC- accredited 'A++' institutions, whereas BHU and Calcutta universities were awarded 'A' grade, but currently their websites are silent about their current grade. There are wide variations in the intake of the Master's program. The University of Madras and Calcutta have 20, whereas Mumbai University and BHU have 30 and 46 seats, respectively. Wide variations are noted in the availability of regular faculty, having only 3 in Madras University and 11 faculty in Mumbai University. BHU and Calcutta University have 8 and 10 regular faculty members. Similarly, variations in the total credits in the master's course are also noted. Calcutta University has 114 credits, whereas BHU has an 80-credit master's program.

The LIS programs are placed under different faculties in all four selected universities. Both traditional as well as modern courses are included in the curriculum of all the universities. Based on the results of the study, it is concluded that the University of Madras, Mumbai, Calcutta, and BHU are the pioneers in LIS education in the country. But there are wide variations about credits, the faculty under which the programs are being run, availability of regular faculty. The traditional and ICT - related papers are being taught in almost all the universities sampled in the study, but as Shukla and Jaiswal (2025) and Jain, Kaur, and Babbar have emphasized, there is a need for revamping the curriculum by integrating AI, data analytics, and digital archiving. And at least some leveling of credits. The most important is the need for regular faculty, which is of utmost importance. Further, it is also suggested that LIS education is to be expanded, and LIS professionals need to be prepared as per the demands of contemporary times.

References

- Ameen, K. (2015). 100 Years' journey at the University of the Punjab: From librarianship in 1915 to information management in 2015. *Pakistan Journal of Information Management and Libraries*, 16, 1-4. Retrieved from <https://pjiml.pu.edu.pk/jo/index.php/pjiml/article/view/173>
- Banaras Hindu University (2025). *Faculty of Arts Library and Information Science*. Retrieved from <https://www.bhu.ac.in>
- Jain, P.K., Kaur, H., & Babbar, P. (2007). *IS education in India: Challenges for students and professionals in the digital age*. Chrome extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/http://eprints.rclis.org/10175/1/D7505896.pdf
- Kanchandani, V. (2019). LIS education in India: Emerging trends and challenges. *Library Herald*, 57(3), 315-326. DOI: 10.5958/0976-2469.2019.00018.6
- Karisiddappa, C. R. (2004). Library and information science curriculum for the knowledge society. *DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology*, 24(3), 3-12.
- Kumar, K., & Sharma, J. (2010). Library and information science education in India: A historical perspective. *DESIDOC Journal of Library and Information Technology*, 30(5), 3-8.
- Kumar, P. S. G. (2008). *Library and information science education in India: Current status and future directions*. New Delhi: B. R. Publishing Corporation.
- Mangla, P. B. (1998). Library and information science education: Trends and issues. In M. K. Jain (Ed.), *Fifty years of library and information services in India* (pp. 285-293). New Delhi: Shipra.
- Singh, S. (2003). Library and information science education in India: Issues and trends. *Malaysian Journal of Library and Information Science*, 8(2), 1-17. Retrieved from <https://ejournal.um.edu.my/index.php/MJLIS/article/view/8389>
- Shukla, P., & Jaiswal, B. (2025). The landscape of LIS education in India: Insights and recommendations for the future. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, 72, 125-137. DOI: 10.56042/alis.v72i2.14925.
- University of Calcutta (2025). *Master of Library and Information Science syllabus*. Retrieved from <https://www.caluniv.ac.in>
- University of Madras (2025). *Department of Library and Information Science*. Retrieved from <https://www.unom.ac.in>
- University of Mumbai (2025). <https://mu.ac.in>

Received October 14, 2025

Revision received October 26, 2025

Accepted October 30, 2025